

THE DIFFERENCES OF GOOD ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15271652>

Abstract. Aim of the research and analysis of pronunciation in English, to promote understanding the theory of pronunciations. Objectives of this work: to study the meaning of pronunciation, identify the different types of pronunciation and to know the ways of pronunciation. Research part: similarities and differences of pronunciation between Kazakh and English languages. Novelty of this research work will help who wants to learn or to begin English. The purpose of pronunciation mastering the skills of speech and varieties of language communication. There isn't much written about intonation the curriculum of a comprehensive school program. We need enrich our knowledge from the pronunciation.

Key words: Pronunciation, phonetics, intonation, stress, accent, rhythm, articulation, phonemes, connected speech.

Annotatsiya. Ingliz tilida talaffuzni tadqiq qilish va tahlil qilishdan maqsad, talaffuz nazariyasini tushunishga yordam berish. Ushbu ishning vazifalari: talaffuzning ma'nosini o'rganish, talaffuzning turli turlarini aniqlash va talaffuz usullarini bilish. Tadqiqot qismi: qozoq va ingliz tillari o'rtasidagi talaffuzdagi o'xshashlik va farqlar. Ushbu tadqiqot ishining yangiligi ingliz tilini o'rganish yoki boshlashni istaganlarga yordam beradi. Talaffuzning maqsadi - nutq ko'nikmalarini o'zlashtirish va til muloqotining turlari. Umumiy maktab dasturining o'quv rejasida intonatsiya haqida ko'p narsa yozilmagan. Biz talaffuzdan bilimimizni boyitishimiz kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: talaffuz, fonetika, intonatsiya, urg'u, ritm, artikulyatsiya, fonemalar, bog'langan nutq.

Аннотация. Целью данного исследования и анализ английского произношения для содействия пониманию теории произношения. Задачи этой работы, во-первых, изучить значение произношения, во-вторых, определить различные виды произношения, и в - третьих, ознакомиться со способами произношения. Исследовательская часть этой статьи — это сходства и различия в произношении казахского и английского языков.

Новизна этого исследования будет полезно для тех, кто хочет изучать или только начинает изучение английского языка. Овладение произношением способствует развитию речевых навыков и разнообразных форм языкового общения. В учебной программе общеобразовательной школы недостаточно материалов по интонации. Нам необходимо обогащать знания в области произношения.

Ключевые слова: Фонетика, интонация, ударение, акцент, ритм, артикуляция, фонемы, связная речь.

I. Introduction

1.1 The aim of research work

Over the years English has become the most popular and spread language in the world. It is the native language of such countries as Great Britain, The United States of America, Canada, Australia and New Zealand. It is also used widely in many European, Asian and African countries for business and studies.

However, the English language plays an important role in our life. English is the international language. Language of diplomacy, business, science, technology, banking, computerizing and medicine field. As such it is a useful and even necessary language.

English is spoken by more people than any other language and is the native language of more than 350 million people.

The aim of research work learning a pronunciation, to develop the pupil’s personality, his way of thinking imagination, hearing, intonation, and creating conditions to use foreign language in speeches. Pronunciation productions plays a huge role in mastering the skills of speech, and in other varieties of language communication.

1.2 The meaning of English pronunciation

The meaning of the English pronunciation of English sounds leads not only to accent, but also to a violation of the meaning of words.

Distortion of speech intonation also leads to an incorrect understanding of the utterances without appropriate explanation and exercises Kazakh students will read and speak English with Kazakh intonation. Every language community has its own social dialect; and consequently its own social accent [Kenesbaev, 1962 p 114]

Speech sounds are divided into vowels and consonants. The main differences between vowels and consonants is as follows. The stream of exhaled air passing through the vocal cords conniving and resulting from vibration goes through the mouth freely and encounters no obstruct [Kenesbaev,1962, p173]

The sounds uttered in such a way are called vowels. At the same muscle tension of the speech organs distributed throughout the speech unit. According to the effects on us, the vowels are based on vibrations of the vocal cords, which produce the basic tone of the vowel. The vowel sound is not only the pitch, but the overtones /higher tones/, which creates a tone. These are the general conditions for the formation of vowel sounds.

Isengeldina uses “The metaphor like in the pronunciation of consonants in the air stream meets epiglottis cavities or that obstacle, the overcoming of which causes noise. At the same muscle tension is concentrated in the place of obstruction. From the acoustic point of view consonant sounds are the noisy. They are formed as a result of non-uniform air temperature fluctuations arising in creating obstacles for the jet of exhaled air. However, there are also, so-called consonants, in which the musical tone of voice dominates the noise [Isengeldind,1960 p 11]

II. Main part

2.1 The types of reading vowels and consonants pronunciation

Here all English sounds. If we want to learn them, we will speak in English as well as native Englishpeople. There are 26 letters,44 sounds, vowels 20, consonants 24.

Diphthongs

Long vowels

Figure 1

Short vowels
 Not in Kazakh
 Different from Kazakh
 Similar with Kazakh

II vowel

Figure 2

There is a tree in front of us, which helps us to pronounce English vowel sounds. All these leaves on the tree are showed level by opening mouse vowels are put from the bottom into top, while opening till clothing . On the left branch the lip will be stretched. On the trunk the lips will be neutral. On the right lips will be round.

Reading Support

Let's gather bouquets from vowels

1) Vowels in open syllable are pronounced as like as in alphabet

[ei]	[i:]	[ai]	[au]	[ju:]
Kate	Pete	Mike	Rose	Susan

2) Vowels in close syllable are pronounced like these

[ae]	[e]	[i]	[ɔ]	[ʌ]
Pat	Ben	Nick, Syd	Tom	mum

3) The words ending with vowel+r pronounce like these:

[a:]	[ə:]	[ə:]	[ɔ]	[ə:]
Mark	Bert	bird	Norman	fur

4) The words ending with a vowel+r+e

[ɛə]	[iə]	[aiə]	[ɔ:]	[juə]
Clare	here	fire	more	pure

2.2 Using consonants in different spheres

Reading of English vowels

If we have knew all the secrets of vowels, let's read these sentences without mistakes and with good pronunciation.

a Kate] has a _____	cat, a car and a hare.
o Rose		dog, a fork, and an ore.
u Susan		cup, a turkey and pure orange juice.
e Pete		pet, and a perfume here
i Mike		pig, a bird and s fire.

Let's read combinations of some vowels:

oo [u] Look, here is a **book**, We can **cook**.

oo [u:] There is a **pool** near our **school**.

ee [i:] I see a **bee** in a **tree**.

ea [i:] I like **tea** and **meat**. I eat **meat**.

Let's learn how to pronounce English consonant sounds:

[h] [n] [ə] [ɝ] [w] [f] [d] [n] [l] [r] [p] These consonants have differences in English pronunciation.

Consonant **[h]** sound. When we pronounce [h] we blow our hands and we feel that it is warm.

Consonant **[p]** sound. This sound pronounce with aspiration when we pronounce [p] we take some peace of papers and blow them. The pieces will scatter. For example: Dandelion will scatter too.

Consonant **[w]** sound. When we pronounce [w] we must pull out lips forward as like as whistling or switch off the candle.

When we pronounce [ə] the tips of the tongue stands between the teeth and a little seen. The top and bottom teeth must be shown as like as you are going to clean them. eg. Three, thank, something.

We must be careful with the sound [s] and [ə] because the English friends don't understand the meaning of the words sink- бату, think- ойлау

Consonant sounds : [t], [d], [n], [t].

When we pronounce these consonant sounds the tip of the tongue concerns the alveol; Where it is on the top of the tooth.

[t] it, ten, tea
[d] dad, red, daddy
[n] nine, fine, nice
[l] listen, lamp, small.

Consonant sound [r]

When we pronounce sound [r] the tip of the tongue has no vibration.

Eg. sorry, brown, grandmother

Consonant sound [n]

When we pronounce [n] the air goes by nose, sound remembers as like as beating

eg. morning, evening, reading.

I take consonants c and g

1) Letter **c** reads like [s] in front of the letters **e, i, y**. eg city, pencil, nice. In other time letter **c** reads like [k] cake, come, act, picture, music.

2) Letter **g** reads like [dʒ] in front of **e, i, y** large, orange, page.

In other time **g** reads like [g] bag, go, big, gas.

Let's find leaves with letter combination ch, ck, ng, sh, ph, th, wh, kn, wr.

Read these letter combination with sentences.

ch [tʃ] The children reach for a peach.

ck [k] Nick has a stick.

ng [ŋ] Sing a song. Bring me a ring. The man is reading.

sh [ʃ] She is in the shop. The fish is in the dish.

ph [f] Phone me. Give me a photograph and a book on geography.

th [θ] [ð] This is a thick book. Thank you.

wh [w] What, where, which, when, why?

kn [n] I know where the knife is.

wr [r] Wrong number. You are wrong.

Consonants on the leaves under row are not made difficulties when we pronounce.

What questions

Questions beginning with question word (where, when, why, what)

Questions beginning with question word pronounce with falling tone

How do you like ~~it~~?

Where do you ~~live~~?

What is your ~~name~~?

Polite requests

Polite requests pronounce with rising tone.

May I ask you a ~~question~~?

May I come ~~in~~?

Shall I ~~read~~?

Imperatives

Imperatives pronounce with falling tone.

Say it a ~~gain~~!

Sit ↘down!
Stop ↘talking!
Go on ↘reading!

General questions

General questions pronounce with rising tone.

Do you like ↗our planet?

Have you got a ↗family?

Have you been to our planet be fore?↗

We will analyze the consonants of the English language.

- [b]
- [p]
- [m]
- [w]
- [v]
- [f]
-

We work out the sounds according to the sheme.

- **Theory:** Let’s examine in detail the mistakes that many students make in the pronunciation .
- **Practice:** practice on a special set of words, patterns.
- **Examples:** We will find significant examples of the use of sound in a famous song.

Consonant [b] sound in English and it’s pronunciation.

Pronounced in the words back, bill, abroad. The articulation of the sound is the same as that of the Kazakh sound [b], but the lips are clenched tighter and the sound is pronounced more intensely.

The task: Practice correct pronunciation in the following words lips need to be squeezed stronger than for the Kazakh sound.

bob [bob]
board [bo:d]
bond [bond]
back [bæk]
bar [ba:r]
boast [bəust]
baby [beibi]
boss [bos]
born [bo:n]
bye [bai]

Another difference sound [b] it is never softened before the vowels of the front row. So, in the word “bill” –hard.

Listen to this “bit by bit” except from the Canadian rock band Mother Mother. It is clearly audible that in the word bit [bit] and in the word by [bai] the sound is equally solid.

Bit by bit

Gonna get my bricks out in the sticks

Bit by bit

Gonna build my house in the wildest thickets.

The task: Practice pronouncing a strong consonant before the front vowels in words. To do this, first utter a firm consonant and only after that lift the middle back of the tongue to the hard palate to pronounce the vowel.

bit	[bit]
bee	[bi:]
beyond	[bijənd]
better	[betər]
beer	[biə]
before	[bɪfɔːr]
be	[bi:]
beach	[bi:tʃ]
beacon	[biːkən]
beef	[biːf]

Consonant sound [p] in English

Pronounced as: park, pure, pilot. The difference from the Kazakh sound is the same: the lips are compressed more closely. Another important detail- the sound is pronounced with a strong aspiration.

The degree of aspiration depends on the position in the word:

- Strong aspiration before unstressed vowel or at the end of a word.
- Virtually absent after the sound.

The task: Practice correct pronunciation of the sound [p] in words.

Lips need to be squeezed harder and breathe the sound.

Poke [pəʊk]

Pair [peə]

Put [pʊt]

Proof [pruːf]

Past [pɑːst]

Pack [pæk]

Poach [pəʊt]

Pod [pɒd]

Pub [pʊb]

The next difference from Kazakh [p] is again the absence of palatalization or softening before the vowels of the front row. So, in the word the «пима»

Sound [p] will be soft, and in the word «пиала» -hard.

The task: Practice pronouncing a solid [p] in front vowels. First say a hard consonant and only then a vowel.

Pick [pɪk]

Pit [pɪt]

Peace [piːs]

Pencil [pensəl]

Peck [pek]

Peach [pi:tʃ]

Pet [pet]

Piano [piənou]

Pill [pil]

Pitch [pitʃ]

English paired consonants [b-p]

In English deaf [p] does not ring back, being in front of a ringing sound: stopbob [stopbob]

A ringing [b] is not stunned in the final position. It becomes weaker and shorter, but otherwise, you can change the meaning of the word: cab- такси cap- қақпақ.

Listen to how we pronounce the word club

We stay in the club we live in the club. We live in the club. We get our car washed in the club. We go to school in the club. We go to the cleaners in the club.

The task:

Before us the words ending in [b] and [p] speak them in accordance with the transcription not stunning sound [b] at the end. Remember that the sound [b] pronounced with partial aspiration.

Cub [k b]

Cup [k p]

Lib [li:b]

Lip [lip]

Pub [p b]

Pup [p p]

Robe [rəub]

Rope [rəup]

Tab [təeb]

Tap [təep]

Cab [kəeb]

Cap [kəep]

Rib [rib]

Rip [rip]

Bub [b b]

Bump [b mp]

Club [kl b]

Clump [kl mp]

When we have mastered all the details of the correct pronunciation, fix the result with patters

For sound [b]

- A British builder built a building of brown bricks. A Bulgarian builder built a building of black bricks.
- A big black bug bit , a big black bear, a big black bear bit, a big black bug.

- A Betty's baby name is Barby. Betty's Barby is a bad-bad boy. Baby Barby is a bad-bad baby. Betty bought a baby boy for a bright blue blanket.

For sound [p]

- Pretty Polly Perkins has a pair of a pickled pepper, a peck of a pickled pepper. If Peter is picked up for a pickled pepper.
- Pablo Picasso put out his Palette, paint box and paintbrushes. Picture of a peaceful place in Paris with a pink palace and a park. What's possible picture price?

Consonant sound [m]

Pronunciation of English sounds in Russian with transcription.

Another sound that comes from the lips. Pronounced in the words mother, my, monkey.

In contrast to the Kazakh sound [m]

Lips again tighten more tightly. Pay attention how tightly press lips, uttering the sound [m] may be longer, shorter depending on the position in the word.

It sounds longer:

-At the end of an isolated word after a short vowel [dim]

-Before the voiced [lambs]

- Before the vowel the vowel [mole]

Sounds shorter to the voiceless consonant [lamp]

The task: Practice correct sound articulation on the following words. Squeeze lips more and remember the positional length of sound.

Mole [məʊl]

Mart [ma:t]

Bloom [blu:m]

Mad [mad]

Bump [bʌmp]

Many [meni]

Champ [tʃɑmp]

Much [mʌtʃ]

Mud [mʌd]

Mock

Mok]

The task: Work hard pronunciation of hard consonant. To do this, first pronounce a vowel consonant, and only after that a vowel.

Milk [milk]

Mickey [miki]

Meal [mi:l]

Mean [mi:n]

Me [mi:]

Meet [mi:t]

Miss [mis]

Met [met]

Melt [melt]
Meddle [medl]

These are all the difficulties associated with the correct pronunciation of the English sound [m]. Therefore, immediately proceeded to the patter:

- There is a lot of memorable monuments.
- Members of the Moslem community
- Miller’s man makes the honey
- A merry miler mills milled at midday. A morose willer mills millet at midnight.

Pronunciation of a consonant sound [w]

Pronounced in the words why, was, warm.

The sound already more complex and has no analogue in our language. Another mistake is to say the same Walter as Walter, that is to replace the sound [w] with Kazakh [y]

How to pronounce this sound.

-Lips are strongly rounded and slightly protruding, forming a narrow circular opening.

-The back of the tongue rises towards the soft palate. The soft plate and lateral edges of the tongue are raised and the air passes along its middle.

-Instantly the tongue and lips move to the position to pronounce the next vowel.

For the correct pronunciation of [w] you need to push the lips forward very energetically, as if you need to blow out a candle and instantly proceed to the articulation of the next after [w] vowel.

Unlike the Kazakh [y] rounded lips, they are not moving forward so much. The sound is pronounced quickly. Lips tight.

The task: Work out the correct pronunciation. Push tight lips into a small hole and push them forward slightly. After pronouncing the sound [w] proceed immediately to the articulation of the next vowel.

What [wat]
Wait [weit]
Win [win]
Wide [waid]
Well [wel]
Wood [wud]
Wall [wa:l]
Will [wil]
Why [wai]
Weak [wi:k]

As an illustrative example, I propose to take Enrique Iglesias’s song “love to see you cry” where the singer very clearly demonstrates the desired position of the lips.

I don’t know why I’m crying for you.

I don’t know why why if just makes me feel alive.

It's imperative to practice distinguishing these sounds IF you replace the sound [w] with [v] you can change the meaning of the word:

Wet-vet

Worse-verse

While-vile

We fix the result with patters:

- Winnie is as weak water.

-Why wouldn't Walter wash with water that wasn't warm.

- Why do you cry, Willy?

Why do you cry?

Why Willy, why Willy?

Why Willy, Why?

So, we have disassembled the labial sounds. Go to the labial tooth.

The pronunciation of sound [v]

The English version is again more intense due to the fact that English speaking people slightly bite the lip, while we simply touch the upper teeth to the lower lip.

The task: Work out the correct pronunciation in words. Remember that you need to tightly press the upper teeth to the lower lip, and the sound should get more intense.

Vocal [vəkəl]

Vote [vəut]

Vase [vɑ:z]

Voter [wəutər]

Volume [vəlʃ:m]

Vocation [vəkeiʃ ən]

Vulgar [vulgər]

The task: Practice pronouncing a firm consonant.

Vain [vein]

Verry

Investigation: At the beginning of the 10 the form after the summer vocation I can't and little forget how to pronounce English words and their rules. But my teacher recommended me to train with my pronunciation.

It was very surprised me to practice with my pronunciation I handed the questionnaire, to the student of our school. It appeared that they practiced just a half an hour on them, some students practiced with pronunciation at all. After that I asked the pupils if they think that pronunciation helped you to read clearly and smooth. Then I spoke with friends. After that I made up my mind to list how pupils practiced with their pronunciation.

These are the questions I asked pupils in the 10 th, 11,th and 9 th forms.

1) How much time do you practice with your pronunciation?

9 th formers answers are;

- No, I don't.

-I practice a little

-I practice more than 10 minutes

-I practice more than 30 minutes.

2)How often do you practice with you pronunciation?

10 th formers answers are;

- I don't practice with my pronunciation
- I really practice with my pronunciation
- I seldom practice with my pronunciation
- I always practice with my pronunciation

3) Do you think that pronunciation helps learning English language?

11 th formers answers are;

- Yes, I do. To my mind pronunciation helps for learning English language.
- No, I don't agree wit you. as for me at first we must learn English grammar.
- I don't know.

Conclusion

English pronunciation will be clear only when we pronounce correctly without pronunciation we loose much of it's variety in speech and writing, reading, learning language.

I think the fact that a person possesses a good pronunciation does not mean that he sounds like a native speaker. The mentality of a nation is expressed not only in lexically correct words, but in a good intonation that depict peculiarities of English language. Pronunciation can be quiet clear if we pronounce clear. Each letters have own rules, intonation because of which letters are occupied. For my work I have chosen how useful English pronunciation to us. My research work is about all the rules of vowels, consonants, theories, examples, differences, practice works and comparing with Kazakh pronunciation. We knew all the secrets of pronunciation and we'll read and write with good pronunciation. I think I have used all about connecting with pronunciation. In future I'll continue my research work when I enter the University.

REFERENCES

1. M.A. Keneshaev Practice pronouncing of English. Мектеп 1962
2. A.R. Isengeldina The pronunciation of sounds. Алматы Мектеп 1960
3. Н. А. Бонк, И.И. Левина, Step by step Москва РОСМЭН 2009
4. V.K. Miller English- Russian Dictionary Moscow 1981
5. Л.П.Христорожественская Английский язык часть I, II Москва Eksino Education 2009
6. Т. Николенко Тесты по фонетике Москва АЙРИС
7. С.Г. Ахметова Қазақша, ағылшынша, орысша сөздік. Алматы. Мектеп 2007
8. Ж.А. Айдарбекова English for beginners. Алматы. Мектеп. 2004
9. Clive Oxeden. Christina Latham Kolnig. Paul Seligson. Happy English New English file. Oxford University Press 2011
3. 10. Dierdre Howard-Williams and Cynthia Herd Word games with English. Cambridge University press 2003
10. Abdullah Hasan Hysal Kose Speed up Turkey Surat English language teaching 2001